

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF PASSION FOR TEACHING ON THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE AND EMPOWERING LEADERSHIP OF SCHOOL HEADS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study was to determine the mediating effect of passion for teaching on the relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads. Utilizing quantitative, non-experimental design via correlational technique, data were obtained from 331 elementary public school teachers who belong to the 2 districts, Bansalan East and Bansalan West under the Division of Davao Del Sur. The researcher utilized total population technique and survey mode of data collection. The researcher also utilized the statistical tools mean, Pearson r and Path Analysis. From the results of the study, it was found out that there is a high level of mean scores for all variables of organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads and very high mean scores for passion for teaching. Also, results revealed that there are significant relationships between organizational culture and between passion for teaching and empowering leadership of school heads. Further, it was revealed that there was a partial mediation effect of passion for teaching on the relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads. This implies that the passion for teaching conveys organizational culture.

Keywords: education, passion for teaching, organizational culture, empowering leadership of school heads, mediating effect, teachers, Philippines

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1. Introduction

The damaging behavior of leaders in the workplace has the potential to trickle down to lower-level personnel in the organization. Bad leadership is one of the potential antecedents of increased turnover intention, employee dissatisfaction, lack of commitment, and psychological stresses such as anxiety, burnout, depression, disengagement, low self-esteem, emotional exhaustion, and employee silence. According to academics, leaders' displays of toxic behavior have a significant and profoundly negative impact on the organizational learning and performance of their organizations (Wolor et al., 2022; Kilian, 2018). In the context of Education, school leader's poor leadership style may prevent teachers from reaching the common good they desire (Bickmore & Dowell, 2018).

Leadership is extremely important for an organization. Great leaders help improve morale in an organization. Even during hard times, effective leaders can help their subordinates be confident and happy in their position. Leadership is the backbone of organizational development because without good leadership it will be difficult to achieve organizational goals. If a leader is trying to influence the behavior of others, then that person needs to think about his or her leadership style (Nurbaeti, 2022). Also, organizational culture is an important topic in scholarly study and business methods, since it is the most crucial element in assessing the effectiveness or failure of an organization. Organizational culture is defined by how employees perceive themselves and how these perceptions shape patterns of trust, values, and expectations. The culture at your organization sets expectations for how people behave and work together, and how well they function as a team. In this way, culture can break down the boundaries between solo teams, guide decision-making, and improve workflow overall. Moreover, researchers concluded that organizational culture was fundamental and of utmost importance to the accomplishment of employees' everyday routines. (Taye et al., 2019; Amtu et al, 2021).

The researcher has not come across a study that deals with organizational culture, empowering leadership of school heads, and passion for teaching in the local setting. Hence, in this perspective, the researcher was interested to determine the significance of the mediating effect of passion for teaching on the relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads using the indicators presented in this study. Through conducting a further examination of organizational culture, the study may provide new insights into how educational organizations build their culture and how teachers maintain their passion for teaching which would help leaders in empowering their teachers. Further, this study can raise concerns for the intended beneficiaries of this study and possibly develop action plans to augment organizational culture, empowering leadership of school heads, and passion for teaching, thus, the need to conduct this study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Organizational Culture

In today's highly competitive setting, reaching targeted organizational productivity levels draws even more attention from both researchers and practitioners. The factors that influence operational performance are investigated with a growing sense of significance. The effect of various organizational cultures on organizational performance is debated where organizational culture is considered one of the key determinants. Significantly, organizational culture influences instructional innovations at universities by allowing or hindering innovation development (Warter, 2019; Caliksan & Zhu, 2021).

Further, by focusing on the six elements of organizational culture (i.e. mission, leadership, knowledge, policy, and socialization), the results of the study have shown that several of the elements of organizational culture are promoting the progress of university missions and visions. More precisely, they report that a welcoming atmosphere is of high importance to both academics and students. Although it is important to recall the university mission statement, practicing it is more important. In addition, a good performance of the member would have a positive impact on the rest of the affiliates and hence there must be close cooperation with all the affiliates of the organization/university, irrespective of their rank or academic standing (Taye et al., 2019).

The first indicator is family orientation or loyalty. An organization's culture is its foundation. And if a firm does not purposefully and knowingly indoctrinate its new hires, its important ideals, principles, and ways of doing things will powerfully socialize everyone who stays with the company. Organizational culture has the potential to be a means of long-term strategic advantage. Employee loyalty is an employee's devotion to an organization or company, as evidenced by his willingness to go above and beyond for the organization or company (Saputra & Mahaputra, 2022).

Moreover, any organization's primary concern is employee loyalty, which is normally determined by the level of services and incentives offered by their employer. Employees who are happy with their employer are more likely to remain with the company for a longer period of time. The employee is one of the essential assets in every company as it determines the smoothness of the overall process. Scholars argue that the effectiveness of the corporation depends well on the performance of workers, while the poor performance of employees is counterproductive to the health of the corporation. Hence, a good organizational culture has a favorable impact on employee satisfaction, while a poor organizational culture leads to negative employee loyalty. (Perez et al., 2018; Razali et al, 2018).

The second indicator is open communication. Culture within an organization is extremely significant and plays a major role in which it is a happy and stable place in which to function. By expressing and fostering the corporate culture of workers, their recognition and appreciation of them can affect their job behavior and attitudes. When the relationship between the leadership and the staff is strong, they will make a greater commitment to team coordination and teamwork and will therefore be motivated to fulfill the task and goals assigned by the organization, thus maximizing work satisfaction. In addition, research shows that work place environment with open communication was found to increase productivity (Hyginus, 2021).

Relating to COVID-19 pandemic, research shows six most successful leadership behaviors within the department should be established in higher education institution, namely, to communicate well on the course of the department, to provide a strong sense of direction and strategic outlook, to provide support and to change workloads to stimulate scholarship and study, to make academic appointments that improve the prestige of the department, allowing the opportunity to participate in decision-making and encouraging open communication and creating a positive and collegial work atmosphere. Further, transparent communication includes a high level of participation by all members of the organization (Virkus & Salman, 2020).

The third indicator is team approach. The culture of an organization determines the proper way of acting within an organization. This culture is made up of common ideals and values developed by leaders and then expressed and repeated through different means, eventually influencing employee attitudes, habits, and understanding. Collaboration and a preference for teamwork are critical in strengthening the practical completion of team tasks. An organizational culture should promote learning systems in which knowledge is created through socialization (Dutta & Rangnekar, 2022).

The last indicator is knowledge of managers. Knowledge management processes are just as important in higher education as they are in the business world. In a study, the following personal traits of successful school administrators stood out as leaders. Characteristics such as being good-natured, hard-working, and patient have been identified as excellent. Having a full understanding of legislation, organizational qualities, taking actions, and having a broad outlook and persuasive skills have been used as managerial attributes. Furthermore, they should also possess technical abilities such as a thorough understanding of curriculum and legislation, effective managerial skills, the capacity to make impartial and rational judgments, and the ability to inspire teachers and students as required. In the context of COVID-19, research points out that the ideals of effective leadership remain constant, i.e. providing a common goal, improving others, handling individuals, and creating power (Leithwood et al., 2020).

2.2 Empowering Leadership of School Heads

Leadership behaviors play a major role in achieving success for educational organizations. Moreover, school leadership is a procedure that motivates and supervises teachers to strive passionately toward achieving educational objectives. Leadership styles and job satisfaction tend to be linked as soon as teachers exercise their duties and duties to get work done by their employees, head teachers apply various forms of leadership, or they may show different patterns of attitude. Leaders who inspire people to act are actually making lively communities and seeing others personally engaged in decision-making (Hinic et al., 2017). Further, research shows that educational leadership has an intermediate and systematic effect at the primary, high school, and middle school levels, according to the standard of instruction at the school. Educational leadership was found to have a comprehensive effect on student achievement in primary school and a medium effect on student achievement in middle school and high school. Also, leadership has recently been conceptualized as a social exchange process (Sehar & Alwi, 2019; Otto et al.,

2021).

In addition, the findings of the study offer valuable input to leaders operating in a global environment in order to develop stronger personal ties with their constituents, thereby enabling them to deliver meaningful outcomes to their organizations. In essence, leadership is not only an improved individual quality, but a way of being and acting in a positive way to connect with others, allowing for cooperation, assistance, and other growth within him (Karadag, 2020; Amtu et al., 2021). Nonetheless, the leader must have an open mission and a common view of the organization and must have the same articulation with each member of staff. This will work as a mirror on which the success of each employee is focused, and this calls for the engagement of workers to shape a company plan that ultimately contributing to the fulfillment of the employee's job (Asghar & Oino, 2017).

The first indicator is leading by example. The relevance of leading by example or role modeling to successful leadership has been recognized in many leadership theories. At the organizational level, empowering leadership has a positive impact on enterprise performance and subordinate behavior. It can be seen that empowering leadership can significantly improve subordinates' attitudes and behavior toward work or organization. Leadership styles including empowering leadership has a significant positive impact on psychological ownership (Li et al., 2018).

The second indicator is participative decision-making. "Influence of engagement in decision making on work satisfaction, group learning, and group involvement," according to Saha and Kumar (2017). Worker satisfaction had a massive and immense courting with inclusion in decision-making, according to the findings. In addition, inclusion in decision-making had a major impact on group learning but had no effect on group engagement. Job satisfaction has a profound and important effect on the group's contribution. Participative leadership increases workforce engagement and growth, and workers' voices are heard when they are respected before work-related choices are taken, to name a few beneficial organizational practices. As such, workers build a sense of being heard and appreciated for their services to the organization by their bosses and superiors (Madsen, 2018).

The third indicator is coaching. Successful leaders, such as effective instructors, adapt and rely on a variety of expertise and techniques based on the context. A traditional school day allows leaders to switch from an authority figure to a teammate, a coach, therapist, navigate between a variety of positions as each demand occurs. The trick to being successful as a leader is the flexibility to change and adapt leadership styles based on what is required (Kerrissey & Edmondson, 2020).

The fourth indicator is informing. Knowledge exchange is simply perceived to be knowledge open to all workers within the company. As long as knowledge is exchanged and circulated, it is widely agreed that it is renewed and converted into a new type, thus becoming a useful feature. Inside the organization, knowledge exchange largely contributes to the production of content. Moreover, leadership efficiency has a direct impact on the performance of organisations and their policies. Analysis reveals that leadership efficiency and information sharing have a positive influence on the company's

approach. This finding may be interpreted as the degree to which the firm's intent or mission has been met. In this case, success may also be described as the assessment of all the efforts made by the company to achieve its objectives (Jyoti & Bhau, 2015).

Furthermore, the practice of transmitting or disseminating information from one individual, a community, or an institution to another person, group, or organization is known as knowledge sharing. Data, which is a valuable commodity in a competitive setting, is shared only on occasion and not at random, and it is important for those who have expertise to choose who and when they share it. Relative to this, according to the findings of a study, both leader efficacy and information sharing actions have a positive impact on the job success of workers within the company. If the top management of the companies uses the leadership qualities they possess in an appropriate and substantive manner, it is extremely likely that they will receive constructive reviews (Sonmez et al., 2020).

The last indicator is showing concern or interacting with the team. Drawing from Longmire and Harrison (2018) who indicated that 'when both perspective and empathic concern are strong, we can feel an acceleration of positive effects,' it would be that perspective and empathic concern have a positive relationship effect that reinforces each other. Additionally, organizations that seek to promote information exchange may also use other practices to convey the advantages of investing in insight and empathic care. As a first step, organizations may need to have instruction in which the essence and advantages of social awareness are explained and learned by employees. Thus, People who feel empathic have an inner desire to help others change their lives, which may include sharing information in an organizational sense (Gerpott et al., 2020).

2.3 Passion for Teaching

Teaching is a very challenging profession, requiring a strong outlook of determination, zeal, and excitement, regardless of the challenges associated with this noble mission. Relative to this, teachers are thought to be the backbone of every educational system in raising the quality of the teaching profession. However, Teachers' performance is influenced by their perseverance and passion in the teaching profession. Teachers must therefore be inspired and committed to fulfilling their enduring goals in order to make a positive impact on the life of their students (Argon & Kaya, 2018; Fabelico & Afalla, 2020).

Moreover, passion in teaching has been described as central to professional motivation and a motivator for learners. Passionate teachers are marked by the passion of innovations that can transform the future for the better, the dedication that can make a difference to the success of learners and the contribution to their academic capacity and job efficiency. In the same manner, passionate teachers enjoy the work they do. They think for the success of their students and actively pursue new ideas to improve their learning. Passionate teachers are mindful of the things that surround them and think of them skillfully in their work. They take their work seriously and are very open to the habits of their students. They collaborate with their peers and students and actively include their students in the learning process. Such a statement implies that all passions are not equal and that while some may result in adaptive outcomes, others may even result in

maladaptive outcomes (Altun, 2017; Vallerand et al., 2020).

Conversely, While certain schools or administrators are able to foster a supportive atmosphere and control demands to some degree, the default environment of children and parents having rights, as well as neoliberal regimes that inform teachers they must obey 'or else,' feed a societal negative attitude toward teachers. These dedicated teachers, who are committed to making excellent efforts for and for students at whatever stage they operate, have a strong sense of judgment and lack of recognition (Fogelgarn, & Burns, 2020).

2.4 Correlation between Measures

Regarding school administrators' key challenge of creating and forming a strong school culture in educational establishments, school administrators should maximize employee loyalty to the organization in order to fulfill individual standards and develop a sustainable school culture. In relation to this, one of the key topics highlighted in school culture study is the strong and weak school culture. Schools with a good school culture are institutions where students and teachers are highly motivated to learn and teach. And where genuine and truthful relationships between school members and a sense of acting together become significant. Administrators in this setting have a common sense of mission and intent, build meaningful relationships with members of the community and turn the school as a sustainable structure into a learning enterprise with the cooperation of all stakeholders (Lee & Louis, 2019).

Accordingly, leadership, school community and organizational image are tightly interlinked ideas. The value of transformative leadership practices shown by school administrators to have a strong school culture and an organizational identity is evident. School managers are the main players in the organization of picture studies and the task of developing a strong school atmosphere in order to improve the preference of educational institutions to the external world. In this sense, it would be useful to have a permanent framework for educational organizations, to cultivate transformative leadership behaviors for school managers, and to coordinate preparation and development activities for a positive school culture and organizational identity. Also, Leadership and organizational culture are also influenced by the organizational commitment of all elements of higher education to working together to improve higher education quality (Kalkan et al., 2020; Amtu et al., 2021).

Over the years, human labour are perceived to be the most valuable assets of any organisation. Human resources are the driving force of an organisation and the use of its capabilities would make a significant contribution to efficiency and competitiveness. In education context, teachers have a very significant role to play in the growth and survival of the organisation. Educational managers should also ensure that their instructors are happy with their profession and loyal to the institution. In reality, a large number of literature and research have shown that workers who are pleased with their work are manifestly loyal to the company. Moreover, in higher education context, specifically in Catholic Higher Education Institutions in the Philippines, it was also discovered how influential the use of clan as a dominant culture form is in retaining higher levels of employee loyalty to their company and improving their satisfaction with their jobs.

(Tindowen, 2019; Wiesner, & Yuniarti, 2018; Batugal, & Tindowen, 2019).

Furthermore, the most operational and professional managers understand the morals directly related to the happiness of employees within their school. Consequently, the quality of school leadership directly affects the choice of the teacher to stay in or leave the teaching profession. Moreover, "surveys show that the satisfaction of teachers has decreased significantly in the last five years, with certain tests at the lowest level in the last 25 years." In hiring and retaining quality educators, there was a need to find out what characteristics educators who were actually teaching are better suited to higher morals as well as what types of leadership, as viewed by teachers (Hickman, 2017).

The above related literature pertains to the variables of the study which are the school heads' leadership behavior, organizational culture and passion for teaching. The findings, readings and studies included are very much related to the study. According to the statements, leadership behavior encompass leading by example, participative decision-making, coaching, informing and showing concern or interacting with the team while organizational culture includes family orientation or loyalty, open communication, team approach, and knowledge of managers. To sum it up, the cited works were in excessive help to unveil possible ways in which school heads' leadership behavior, organizational culture and passion for teaching were related with one another. These would also serve as a support to the presentation, results and findings of the study.

The study is anchored with the theory of Vallerand et al. (2008) that "passion is a strong inclination or desire toward an activity (e.g., one's job) that one likes (or even loves) and finds important and in which one invests time and energy". Based on the principle of self-determination, Vallerand et al. (2003) identified two distinct forms of passion, harmonious passion and obsessive passion, based on the mechanism of internalization that contributes to one's personality. From this angle, harmoniously passionate teaching can be seen as filling a substantial but not overwhelming space within the personality of the teacher and as being in balance with other facets of the life of the teacher. This allows teachers to completely concentrate on teaching-related activities and to focus their time and energies on other tasks at hand without inclining to teaching.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Research Subjects

The respondents of the study were the public the elementary school teachers in the municipality of Bansalan. The researcher made use of universal sampling and which means everyone was given a chance to be included in the study. Stehman and Overton (2020) stated that complete counts are a complete enumeration (census) of individuals within a sampling unit. Thus, a random sample of quadrats might be drawn, and all the individuals counted on each of the quadrats. Futher, there were 352 total public elementary school teachers in Bansalan- East and West District. Since the researcher made use of universal sampling, all the teachers in both districts will be part of the study. Teachers who were given the opportunity for substitution will not be considered as participants of this study. Also, those teachers who availed teaching opportunity through the Local School Board (LSB) and Provincial School Board (PSB). During the survey, only

331 were involved, the rest were excluded based on the exclusion criteria.

Moreover, those teachers who are processing for transfer and teachers who have applied for total withdrawal of participation are likewise not qualified. Subjects who are not willing to sign the informed consent will not be included in the study. Respondents have the right to withdraw from research at any time. If a respondent decides to withdraw from the research study, the researcher will discontinue to use his/her responses involving his/her participation in the study. On the other hand, the researcher may decide to terminate a subject's participation in research if deemed necessary regardless of whether the subject wishes to continue participating.

The respondents were chosen accordingly to answer the questionnaire with confidentiality. The target respondents were free to decline from participating the survey. They were not forced to answer the research questionnaire and were encouraged to return the same to the researcher for its automatic disposal. Moreover, they can withdraw anytime their participation in the research process if they felt uncomfortable about the study since they are given the free-will to participate without any form of consequence or penalty. The study covered the period from October 2020- November 2022.

This study was conducted in public elementary schools in Bansalan, specifically in the two districts of Bansalan: Bansalan East and Bansalan West. Bansalan is situated at the north-western part of the Province of Davao del Sur. Towards the south is the Municipality of Matanao, to the west is the Municipality of Magsaysay, to the southeast is the Municipality of Digos and on the north-east lies the Mt. Apo National Park. Its total land area is 48,548 hectares and divided into 23 villages or barrios where the poblacion is the main center.

The researcher believed that this was the appropriate locale of the study because it has a good number of respondents who can ensure concrete results of the study and the researcher has not come across a study using the variables on organizational culture, empowering leadership of school heads, and passion for teaching in the local setting. Moreover, in the aforementioned areas under study, the existing situation of teachers showed that they were still in the adjustment period after the traumatic experiences brought about by the pandemic. This has affected their level of organizational culture, leadership of school heads, and passion for teaching which needed to be checked and revisited especially since almost all classes are going back to the face-to-face mode of learning.

3.2 Materials/ Instruments

The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections and included and integrated in the paper. The final copies were submitted to a panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 4.43 which has a verbal description of very good.

Further, before the administration of the research instrument, a pilot testing was done on selected public school teachers, who were not the respondents of the study. With

the pilot testing, the reliability of the scales was established using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, with the results: 0.963 for Organizational Culture, 0.986 for empowering leadership of school heads and 0.982 for passion for teaching.

3.3 Design and Procedure

This study used a non-experimental quantitative design using a descriptive analysis correlation methodology designed to collect evidence, concepts, details and knowledge specific to the study. In non-experimental studies, researchers gather results without modifying or adding therapies (Gehle, 2013). In this study the variables were not manipulated and the setting was not controlled. Descriptive-correlation research design describes and interprets what is, and reveals conditions and relationships that exist and do not exist. Further it is a fact finding study that allowed the researcher to examine characteristics, behaviors, and experiences of study participants (Calderon, 2006; Calmorin, 2007).

Moreover, a mediation model was used in this study. The mediation model is one that seeks to identify and explicate the mechanism or process that underlies an observed relationship between an independent variable (organizational culture) and a dependent variable (empowering leadership of school heads) via the inclusion of a third explanatory variable, known as a mediator variable (passion for teaching). Rather than hypothesizing a direct causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, a mediational model hypothesizes that the independent variable influences the mediator variable, which in turn influences the dependent variable. Thus, the mediator variable serves to clarify the nature of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In other words, mediating relationships occur when a third variable plays an important role in governing the relationship between the other two variables (MacKinnon, 2008).

To illustrate, mediation analysis was used in social sciences and other fields in order to evaluate the mechanism through which an independent variable (X) affects a dependent variable (Y). The variable transmitting the influence of the independent variable onto the dependent variable is called the mediator (M), and the indirect effect through the mediator is called the mediated effect.

This study followed the systematic procedures in the conduct of the research. First, before the conduct of the study, the researcher sent a letter asking for permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Department of Education Division of Davao del Sur. This letter once approved was furnished to the School Heads of the participants. Once approved, the survey questionnaire was administered to the respondents of the 2 Districts in Bansalan, Davao del Sur. As soon as request was approved and strictly observing the safety protocols in this pandemic time as per mandate by the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Emerging Infectious Disease (COVID 19) such as physical/social distancing and wearing of face masks, the researcher immediately visited the concerned school heads of the schools, as part of the courtesy call and discussed the plan on the conduct of online survey thru google forms to all concerned respondents.

During the courtesy call, a list and contact numbers/email addresses of all

respondents/students were requested from the offices of the concerned school heads/principals. The list served as the basis for the researcher for the data gathering which activity took around one month from the sending of the survey questionnaire to all the respondents in google forms up to the retrieval of the accomplished survey questionnaires. Also, before the actual data collection, the researcher secured Certificate of Compliance from UMERC to ensure compliance of some ethical considerations in research.

All retrieved questionnaires were encoded in the excel template after verification and checking as to completeness of the answers. After all the tallying and validating of results, the data was analysed and interpreted in line with the objectives of the study. Based from the findings of the study, conclusions and recommendations were formulated.

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data and testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance: Mean was used to determine the levels of instructional leadership, teacher collegiality and professional development of teachers; Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was used to determine the significance of the relationship between and among instructional leadership, teacher collegiality and professional development of teachers; and Medgraph using Sobel z -test was used to determine the significance of the mediation of teacher collegiality on the relationship between instructional leadership and professional development of teachers.

In the conduct of this study especially before the data was gathered, ethical issues and considerations will be dealt. The researcher underwent evaluation conducted by the members of ethics review committee. After several review process, this study was marked as passed and approved by the UM Ethics Review Committee (UMERC) with UMERC Protocol Number 2022-156. The participation of the respondents was completely voluntary and anonymous to protect their privacy and information was given whenever the respondents did not understand, before deciding whether to participate or not in the study. As a researcher, all data gathered were kept confidential and that such information was only be utilized for the purpose of the research. Informed consent was secured from all the respondents involved in the study.

The participants were carefully selected based on the criteria provided in the research. The criteria in the selection of respondents included only those who are elementary public school teachers in the two districts in Bansalan, Davao del Sur. The study did not involve in high risks of situations that the respondents may experience since the respondents public elementary school teachers and this was conducted in accordance to due process. All the teachers are the primary beneficiaries of the study. The study used the Grammarly or Turnitin software and/ or Plagiarism Detector to ensure that there was no plagiarism that happened in the whole duration of the study. The study underwent the standard procedure of research established by the Professional Schools of the University of Mindanao. There was no evidence that the study was intentionally misrepresented to match a model or theoretical assumption. The study had no conflict of interest since the researcher has no relationship to the respondents of the study, but it was a requirement for the completion of the master degree in education at the University of Mindanao Professional Schools.

In this study, there was no deceit. The researcher secured proper permission from the targeted schools where the respondents are teaching/working. Considering the risks of COVID-19, and in the conduct of the online data gathering, the researcher utilized Google Forms where the respondents indicated their responses on the specific item-questions being asked. No person was authorized to publish nor present this paper except the researcher or the adviser without the consent of the researcher.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1: Level of Organizational Culture

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Family Orientation/Loyalty	3.97	0.65	High
Open Communication	3.98	0.73	High
Team Approach	3.89	0.67	High
Knowledge of Managers	3.77	0.77	High
Overall	3.90	0.67	High

The level of organizational culture is high due to the high levels of responses. The indicators family orientation or loyalty, open communication, team approach, and knowledge of managers. These indicators are arranged from highest to lowest. The high level of open communication suggests that teachers and school heads practice open communication in their workplace. This is relative to the idea of Hyginus (2021) who stated that culture within an organization is extremely significant and plays a major role in which it is a happy and stable place in which to function. By expressing and fostering the corporate culture of workers, their recognition and appreciation of them can affect their job behavior and attitudes. When the relationship between the leadership and the staff is strong, they will make a greater commitment to team coordination and teamwork and will therefore be motivated to fulfill the task and goals assigned by the organization, thus maximizing work satisfaction.

In addition, the high level of family orientation or loyalty shows that the teachers has created a sense of loyalty towards their organization. This is aligned to the study of Saputra and Mahaputra (2022) who stated that an organization's culture is its foundation. And if a firm does not purposefully and knowingly indoctrinate its new hires, its important ideals, principles, and ways of doing things will powerfully socialize everyone who stays with the company.

Moreover, the high level of team approach suggests that teamwork is evident in the organization. The culture of an organization determines the proper way of acting within an organization. This culture is made up of common ideals and values developed by leaders and then expressed and repeated through different means, eventually influencing employee attitudes, habits, and understanding. Collaboration and a preference for teamwork are critical in strengthening the practical completion of team tasks. An organizational culture should promote learning systems in which knowledge is created through socialization (Dutta & Rangnekar, 2022).

Lastly, the high level of knowledge of managers suggests that it is very evident that

school heads and principals are well-oriented and knowledgeable of their duties and responsibilities. This is relative to the argument of Leithwood et al. (2020) who stated that knowledge in management will lead to increased decision-making skills, shorter “product” production cycle times (for example, program development and testing outputs), enhanced education and administrative services, and lower costs if performed correctly.

Table 2: Level of Empowering Leadership of School Heads

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Leading by Example	3.85	0.70	High
Participative Decision-Making	3.79	0.69	High
Coaching	3.76	0.74	High
Informing	3.72	0.75	High
Showing Concern/Interacting with the Team	3.76	0.81	High
Overall	3.78	0.71	High

The very high level of empowering leadership of school heads resulted from the high levels of responses. The indicators leading by example, participative decision-making, coaching, informing, and showing concern or interacting with team were arranged from highest to lowest. The high level of leading by example suggests that the school heads were able to set as an example to their teachers. This is relative to Li et al.’s (2018) idea that the organizational level, empowering leadership has a positive impact on enterprise performance and subordinate behavior. It can be seen that empowering leadership can significantly improve subordinates' attitudes and behavior toward work or organization. Leadership styles including empowering leadership has a significant positive impact on psychological ownership.

Moreover, the high level of participative decision-making shows that school heads have encouraged participation in the organization in making decisions. This is in line with the argument of Madsen (2018) who stated that worker satisfaction had a massive and immense courting with inclusion in decision-making. In addition, inclusion in decision-making had a major impact on group learning but had no effect on group engagement. Job satisfaction has a profound and important effect on the group's contribution. In other words, persons with a high sense of involvement in decision-making under conditions with high sense of work characteristics are reflective of their substantial degrees of organizational contribution. Participative leadership increases workforce engagement and growth, and workers' voices are heard when they are respected before work-related choices are taken, to name a few beneficial organizational practices. As such, workers build a sense of being heard and appreciated for their services to the organization by their bosses and superiors.

In addition, the high level of coaching suggests that school heads served as mentors and coaches to their teachers. This is relative with the idea of Kerrissey and Edmondson (2020) that successful leaders, such as effective instructors, adapt and rely on a variety of expertise and techniques based on the context. A traditional school day allows leaders to switch from an authority figure to a teammate, a coach, and therapist, navigate between

a variety of positions as each demand occurs. The trick to being successful as a leader is the flexibility to change and adapt leadership styles based on what is required.

Furthermore, the high level of showing concern or interacting with the team shows that school heads have meaningfully shown their concern and were able to interact with the teachers. Drawing from Longmire and Harrison (2018) who indicated that 'when both perspective and empathic concern are strong, we can feel an acceleration of positive effects,' it would be that perspective and empathic concern have a positive relationship effect that reinforces each other. Additionally, the result is relative to the study of Gerpott et al. (2020) that organizations who seek to promote information exchange may also use other practices to convey the advantages of investing in insight and empathic care. As a first step, organizations may need to have instruction in which the essence and advantages of social awareness are explained and learned by employees. Thus, People who feel empathic have an inner desire to help others change their lives, which may include sharing information in an organizational sense.

Lastly, the high level of informing shows that school heads were able to update and disseminate information necessary in the organization. The practice of transmitting or disseminating information from one individual, a community, or an institution to another person, group, or organization is known as knowledge sharing. Data, which is a valuable commodity in a competitive setting, is shared only on occasion and not at random, and it is important for those who have expertise to choose who and when they share it. Relative to this, according to the findings of a study, both leader efficacy and information sharing actions have a positive impact on the job success of workers within the company. If the top management of the companies uses the leadership qualities they possess in an appropriate and substantive manner, it is extremely likely that they will receive constructive reviews (Sonmez et al., 2020).

Table 3: Level of Passion for Teaching

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
I spend a lot of time doing my job as a teacher.	4.22	0.48	Very High
I like my job as a teacher.	4.40	0.55	Very High
My job as a teacher is important for me.	4.65	0.52	Very High
My job as a teacher is a passion for me.	4.37	0.55	Very High
My job as a teacher is in harmony with the other activities in my life.	4.39	0.58	Very High
I have difficulties controlling my urge to do my job as a teacher.	3.58	0.99	High
The new things that I discover doing my job as a teacher allow me to appreciate it even more.	4.39	0.57	Very High
I have almost an obsessive feeling for my job as a teacher.	3.65	0.95	High
My job as a teacher reflects the qualities I like about myself.	4.18	0.49	High
My job as a teacher allows me to live a variety of experiences.	4.38	0.53	Very High
My job as a teacher is the only thing that really turns me on.	3.59	0.94	High
My job as a teacher is well integrated in my life.	4.13	0.51	High
If I could, I would only do my job as a teacher.	3.65	0.93	High
My job as a teacher is in harmony with other things that are part of me.	4.12	0.54	High
My job as a teacher is so exciting that I sometimes lose control over it.	3.66	0.92	High
I have the impression that my job as a teacher controls me.	3.48	1.21	High
Overall	4.05	0.46	High

All the responses resulted to the high level of passion for teaching. This indicates that the elementary public school teachers have maintained their passion for teaching throughout their years of teaching. This is relative to the idea of Altun (2017) and Vallerand et al. (2020) that passionate teachers are marked by the passion of innovations that can transform the future for the better, the dedication that can make a difference to the success of learners and the contribution to their academic capacity and job efficiency. In the same manner, passionate teachers enjoy the work they do. They think for the success of their students and actively pursue new ideas to improve their learning.

Table 4.1: Significant Relationship between Organizational Culture and Empowering Leadership of School Heads

Organizational Culture	Empowering Leadership of School Heads					Overall
	ELSH-LE	ELSH-PDM	ELSH-C	ELSH-I	ELSH-SC/IT	
FO/L	0.774 <.001	0.832 <.001	0.837 <.001	0.779 <.001	0.827 <.001	0.842 <.001
OC	0.737 <.001	0.859 <.001	0.791 <.001	0.754 <.001	0.822 <.001	0.823 <.001
TA	0.799 <.001	0.848 <.001	0.842 <.001	0.802 <.001	0.811 <.001	0.852 <.001
KM	0.840 <.001	0.831 <.001	0.891 <.001	0.856 <.001	0.862 <.001	0.890 <.001
Overall	0.830 <.001	0.887 <.001	0.886 <.001	0.841 <.001	0.875 <.001	0.897 <.001

Presented in Table 4.1 is the correlation between measures of organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads. It can be seen from the table that the correlation gained an overall r-value of 0.897 with p-value <0.001 which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that there is significant relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads is rejected. It can also be gleaned from the table that organizational culture is significantly correlated to empowering leadership of school heads, since the indicators revealed the following overall r-values: family orientation or loyalty with 0.842, open communication with 0.823, team approach with 0.852, and knowledge of managers with 0.890; and the p-value is <0.001. Thus, the two variables are significantly associated.

The correlation between measures of organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads revealed a significant relationship. This implies that organizational culture is significantly correlated with empowering leadership of school heads. The findings of the study were relative to the idea of Kalkan et al. (2020) and Amtu et al. (2021) that leadership, school community and organizational image are tightly interlinked ideas. The value of transformative leadership practices shown by school administrators to have a strong school culture and an organizational identity is evident. School managers are the main players in the organization of picture studies and the task of developing a strong school atmosphere in order to improve the preference of educational institutions to the external world. In this sense, it would be useful to have a permanent framework for educational organizations, to cultivate transformative leadership behaviors for school managers, and to coordinate preparation and development activities for a positive school culture and organizational identity. Also, Leadership and organizational culture are also influenced by the organizational commitment of all elements of higher education to working together to improve higher education quality.

Table 4.2: Significant Relationship between Organizational Culture and Passion for Teaching

Organizational Culture	Passion for Teaching
FO/L	0.336 <.001
OC	0.300 <.001
TA	0.367 0.001
KM	0.461 <.001
Overall	0.388 <.001

The data also revealed that organizational culture is positively correlated with passion for teaching as indicated by the overall r-values of the following measures: family orientation or loyalty with 0.336, open communication with 0.300, team approach with

0.367, and knowledge of managers with 0.461; and the p-value is <0.001. Thus, the two variables are significantly associated.

Overall, organizational culture is significantly related to passion for teaching with $r = 0.388$ at $p = 0.000 < 0.001$, however, the correlation is a weak positive one. The indicator knowledge of managers predicts passion for teaching at $r=0.461$, which is the highest among all indicators.

The correlation between the indicators of organizational culture and passion for teaching revealed a significant relationship. This implies that organizational culture is positively correlated with passion for teaching. The result of this study is relative to the statements of Lee and Louis (2019) regarding school administrators' key challenge of creating and forming a strong school culture in educational establishments, school administrators should maximize employee loyalty to the organization in order to fulfill individual standards and develop a sustainable school culture. In relation to this, one of the key topics highlighted in school culture study is the strong and weak school culture. Schools with a good school culture are institutions where students and teachers are highly motivated to learn and teach. And where genuine and truthful relationships between school members and a sense of acting together become significant. Administrators in this setting have a common sense of mission and intent, build meaningful relationships with members of the community and turn the school as a sustainable structure into a learning enterprise with the cooperation of all stakeholders.

Table 4.3: Significant Relationship between Passion for Teaching and Empowering Leadership of School Heads

	Empowering Leadership of School Heads					Overall
	ELSH-LE	ELSH-PDM	ELSH-C	ELSH-I	ELSH-SC/IT	
Passion for Teaching	0.445 <.001	0.382 <.001	0.465 <.001	0.473 <.001	0.460 <.001	0.464 <.001

Presented in Table 4.3 is the correlation between passion for teaching and empowering leadership of school heads. It can be seen from the table that the correlation gained an overall r-value of 0.464 and the p-value <0.001 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the correlation between passion for teaching and empowering leadership of school heads is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between passion for teaching and empowering leadership of school heads is rejected. Data also revealed that when passion for teaching is correlated with empowering leadership of school heads, the following overall r-values are revealed: leading by example with 0.445, participative decision-making with 0.382, coaching with 0.465, informing with 0.473, and showing concern or interacting with the team with 0.460.

These indicate that the two variables are significantly associated. Among all the indicators of empowering leadership, passion for teaching best predicts the indicator informing with $r=0.473$, significant at $p\text{-value}=0.000 < 0.001$.

The correlation between the indicators of organizational culture and passion for

teaching revealed a significant relationship. This implies that passion for teaching is positively correlated with empowering leadership of school heads. The result of this study is in line with the argument of Batugal and Tindowen (2019) who stated that human labour are perceived to be the most valuable assets of any organization. Human resources are the driving force of an organization and the use of its capabilities would make a significant contribution to efficiency and competitiveness. In education context, teachers have a very significant role to play in the growth and survival of the organization. Educational managers should also ensure that their instructors are happy with their profession and loyal to the institution. In reality, a large number of literature and research have shown that workers who are pleased with their work are manifestly loyal to the company. Moreover, in higher education context, specifically in Catholic Higher Education Institutions in the Philippines, it was also discovered how influential the use of clan as a dominant culture form is in retaining higher levels of employee loyalty to their company and improving their satisfaction with their jobs.

Table 5: Regression results of the variables in the criteria of the presence of mediating effect

Effect	Label	Estimate	SE	95% Confidence Interval		Z	p	% Mediation
				Lower	Upper			
Indirect	a × b	0.056	0.013	0.031	0.08148	4.87	< .001	5.88
Direct	c	0.896	0.027	0.843	0.94892	18.73	< .001	94.12
Total	c + a × b	0.952	0.026	0.901	1.00296	23.93	< .001	100.0

There are three steps to be met for a third variable to be acting as a mediator. In Table 5, these are categorized as Steps 1 to 3. In step 1, organizational culture as the independent variable (IV) significantly predicts empowering leadership of school heads, which is the dependent variable (DV) of the study. In step 2, organizational culture significantly predicts passion for teaching, the mediator (M). In step 3, organizational culture significantly predicts a empowering leadership of school heads. Because the three steps (paths a, b and c) are significant, further mediation analysis through Medgraph is necessary, including the Sobel z test to assess the significance of the mediation effect. If the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable becomes non-significant at the final step of the analysis, full mediation will be achieved. It means all the effects are mediated by the mediator variable. In addition, if the regression coefficient is substantially reduced at the final step but remains significant, only partial mediation is obtained, which implies that part of the independent variable (organizational culture) is mediated by the mediator (passion for teaching) but other parts are either direct or mediated by other variables that are not included in the model. The ratio index is computed by dividing the indirect effect by the total effect; in this case, 0.056 by 0.952 equals 0.058. It seems that about 5.88 percent of the total effect of organizational culture on empowering leadership of school heads goes through passion for teaching, and about 94.12% of the total effect is either direct or mediated by other variables not included in the model.

5. Recommendations

The researcher came up with recommendations based on the results of the study. On the very high ratings of passion for teaching, high ratings of organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads, the researcher recommends that the school may strengthen its organizational culture by promoting collaborative decision-making; this can be done with the initiative of school heads and managers. Considering that conflicts may also arise in any organization, the researcher recommends that schools may also adopt restorative approaches to discipline; in this way, strong relationships among workers can be achieved. Moreover, it is also important to consider open communication in the organization as this will help to harmonize the mood in the workplace. School management may also conduct a yearly re-orientation of the school's mission and vision to remind the teachers and stakeholders of its goal.

Moreover, the Department of Education may continue to provide leadership seminars to school heads and skill-related seminars to teachers. These seminars and training are necessary for the professional growth and development of both school heads and teachers. Also, considering that feedback and coaching are essential in teaching, school heads may continue to provide regular and constructive feedback and coaching to teachers. Moreover, DepEd may also create a policy on the mandatory evaluation of School heads by teachers. This might help school heads on practicing self-regulation and improve their leadership methods. The researcher also recommends that school heads may encourage lifelong learning and professional advancement among teachers.

In addition, it is also essential that schools may conduct activities that would ignite and cultivate a passion for teaching among teachers. Specifically, it may be helpful to conduct seminars on 21st Century teaching strategies and innovations in teaching methods and assessments. Another, conducting activities that would regulate the mental and emotional well-being of teachers may significantly contribute to teachers' productivity and may increase their passion for teaching.

On the results of the partial mediating effect of passion for teaching on the relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads, the researcher recommends that there may always be a policy of open communication and collaborative decision-making in school. The school management may listen to the ideas of the teachers and allow them to participate in discussions relating to the plans and programs for the school and the students. The school head themselves may always encourage themselves to join training and seminars that would develop and enhance their leadership skills. The Department of Education may conduct a policy on school heads' leadership evaluation by teachers. Lastly, the school heads may always cultivate and put high regard on teachers' passion for teaching and continuous professional development.

6. Conclusion

With consideration on the findings of the study, conclusions were drawn in this

section. There is a high level of passion for teaching, a high level of organizational culture and a high level of empowering leadership of school heads. There is a significant relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads. There is also a significant relationship between organizational culture and passion for teaching, and a significant relationship between passion for teaching and empowering leadership of school heads. The findings of the study clearly confirm the notion about the mediating effect of passion for teaching on the relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads. In addition, there is also a partial mediation on the effect of passion for teaching on the relationship between organizational culture and empowering leadership of school heads.

The findings are supported by the Organizational Culture and Leadership theory of by Schein (1992) which stated that culture is the result of a complex group learning process that is only partially influenced by leader behavior. But if the group's survival is threatened because elements of its culture have become maladapted, it is ultimately the function of leadership at all levels of the organization to recognize and do something about this situation. It is in this sense that leadership and culture are conceptually intertwined. The theory highlighted that the only thing of real importance that leaders do is to create and manage culture; that the unique talent of leaders is their ability to understand and work with culture; and that it is an ultimate act of leadership to destroy culture when it is viewed as dysfunctional. The findings were interpreted as a general acceptance of the hypothesis.

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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